

Risk-Sharing Contracts and Risk Management of Bilateral Contracting in Electricity Markets*

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Abstract

The liberalization of the electricity sector has conducted to the establishment of spot markets, derivative markets and private bilateral contracts to trade electricity, increasing the competition in the sector. Spot markets are composed of day-ahead, intraday and real-time markets, and their prices are highly volatile. Derivative markets are composed of physical and financial products to hedge against spot price volatility. Players can set the terms and conditions of private bilateral contracts but these have several risks that can be mitigated using a risk management process composed of three phases: risk assessment, characterization and hedging. This paper focuses on both risk attitude and risk-sharing, and how they can influence the negotiation of the price. It presents the standard and non-standard designs of a new type of contract, the Risk-Sharing Contract (RSC). Furthermore, it describes the trading process of these contracts and introduces a negotiation strategy for dealing with risk. It also presents case studies on bilateral contracting involving the negotiation of RSCs, where different demand and supply agents interact and trade according to the rules of an alternating offers protocol. Results from the case studies prove the benefit of RSCs to hedging against spot price volatility, benefiting risk-averse players by reducing the price risk and conducting mutually beneficial agreements. While the use of derivatives products can conduct losses/revenues between -15% and 3% concerning the spot market, by using non-standard RSCs those outputs vary between -1% and 3% with substantially less risk.

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1. Introduction

The liberalization of the electricity sector has resulted in a wholesale market for electricity production, and a retail market for electricity trading. This market structure was created to obtain competitive market prices of electricity and decrease its net cost through an increase in concurrence [1]. In wholesale markets, producers trade electricity with retailers and large consumers, facing the risk of future changes in the market prices, such as in the quantities required by demand-side players [2–4]. In retail markets, retailers normally consider fixed tariffs when signing private bilateral contracts with customers, being subject to their uncertain consumption (quantity risk) and also to the price volatility (price risk) of spot markets, where they can acquire the energy required by their consumers [5, 6]. In liberalized markets, normally the tariffs offered to consumers are revised periodically, and consumers are free to change their supplier. So, retailers support all risks, being the risk asymmetry between retailers and consumers substantial [7, 8]. Spot markets are commonly divided in day-ahead, intraday and real-time markets, where supply and demand agents submit their bids. These markets close before real-time commitment, existing balancing markets to fix short-run deviations between supply and demand [9].

Traditionally, governments stimulated the installation of new non-mature variable renewable energy sources (VRES), such as tidal and wave power, by proposing feed-in-tariffs or other incentives for a fixed period, when they are passive players, dealing only with operational and maintenance issues [10, 11]. After that period, these technologies have to be active players, start bidding their power forecasts at markets, subject to quantity and price uncertainty [9]. VRES are characterized by near-zero variable costs of production, decreasing market prices and consequently their return from markets [12, 13]. Furthermore, the increase in the penetration of mature VRES, such as wind power and photovoltaic, increases the variability and uncertainty of the prices at spot markets. [14, 15]. VRES and demand-side players, as retailers, face the uncertainty related to their real-time production and consumption, respectively, paying high penalties for their deviations [16–18]. While these penalties are reflected in retail tariffs and the VRES levelized cost of energy,

Nomenclature

Acronyms and Abbreviations

BRP	Balance Responsible Party
CfD	Contract for Differences
CVaR	conditional VaR
DAM	day-ahead market
MIBEL	Iberian Electricity Market
mu	monetary unit
NYMEX	New York Mercantile Exchange
OMIE	the Spanish electricity market operator
OMIP	the Portuguese electricity market operator
RSC	Risk-Sharing Contract
VaR	Value-at-Risk
VRES	variable renewable energy sources

C	maximum concession factor
C_{fN}	concession factor of a risk-neutral agent
C_f	concession factor
$max_{i,p}$	maximum compensation
p	price
q	quantity
$r_{p,t}$	reference price
$s_{p,t}$	strike price
U	additive function or global utility
v	(marginal) utility
$X_{n,max}$	maximum expected value of issue
$X_{n,min}$	minimum expected value of issue
x_n	issue

Symbols

β_0	risk-sharing indexed to the negotiated item
β_i	risk-sharing indexed to other items
Γ	electricity cost
λ	risk attitude or preference
π_n	probability of occurrence or weight
Π	profit with electricity trading
σ_i	uncertainty
\mathcal{A}	agents
$\overline{cp_{i,t,p}}$	arithmetic average of the market clearing price
a_b	buyer agent
a_s	seller agent

Subscripts

H	number of clearing periods
h	clearing period
I	number of items
i	items
j	agent index
K	number of proposals
k	proposal
N	number of issues
n	issue number
O	number of bilateral contract's options
o	bilateral contract's option
P	number of periods
p	period
T	number of time horizons
t	time horizon

without incentives new VRES are subject to a high risk of investment [8, 19]. Currently, new projects of these technologies have difficulties being financed, having to compete in new capacity auctions promoted by governments [10]. To face these difficulties and hedge against this uncertainty, market players can trade bilateral contracts on derivative markets or negotiate private bilateral contracts, setting the terms and conditions of agreements [20–22]. Against this background, VRES need to use strategic bidding to mitigate both the risk of price volatility and their production uncertainty, increasing their profit from wholesale markets [23–26].

The existence of a robust bilateral market is often considered a crucial prerequisite to mitigate the market power in energy markets. For this to occur there has to be a sufficient incentive for both parties to transact in the bilateral market, leading to symmetrical risks and comparable judgments of an acceptable price at which to transact. Bilateral contracts are divided into physical and financial contracts [1]. Standard contracts can be negotiated in the derivatives markets, using the energy exchanges, while non-standard contracts can be negotiated privately (see [27] for a detailed description). In bilateral contracts, the only parameters that commonly have to be communicated to the market operator are the date (specific day(s) and hour(s)), the quantity, and the input and output grid nodes in the case of physical contracts. The main limitation of the financial contracts is that does not exist a physical transaction of electricity. So, agents may have to bid for electricity at spot markets or sign private bilateral contracts if they want to trade electricity. One of the biggest issues of bilateral contracts is that mainly only forward contracts are used as physical contracts (futures contracts are riskier, and options are more expensive). However, while bilateral contracts are recognized as very important to the functioning of competitive electricity markets, there are several obstacles to long-term bilateral contracting. Chief among these is risk asymmetry because buyers face greater risks than sellers in waiting to transact in spot markets. So, sellers may charge a substantial risk premium for long-term bilateral contracts. Sellers have almost nothing to lose by waiting to transact in spot markets in which they will face bid-based clearing prices. They have potential for windfall profits at very low risk because they cannot be forced to sell below the prices they offered [28].

Commodity speculation is one of the reasons that increases the price risk of long-term bilateral contracts, mainly is cases of political uncertainty [1]. A risk management process shall be followed to quantify and deal with these risks. A risk management process normally starts with the risk

assessment phase where all risk factors are identified and analysed, followed by a risk characterization method, where metrics, like Value-at-Risk (VaR) and conditional VaR (CVaR) are used to measure the risks, and finally, it ends with a risk hedging phase, where some actions are performed to mitigate those risks [29].

This article aims to demonstrate that if sellers share part of their market risks with buyers, they can achieve a mutually beneficial deal. Against this background, it focuses on the model of a new type of contract, the Risk-Sharing Contract (RSC). This type of contract has standard and non-standard versions, allowing players to share their contracts' risks. Depending on the sellers' risk-sharing magnitude, sellers may decrease their required risk premium and offer more competitive prices to buyers. Accordingly, this article presents several key features of software agents able to negotiate RSCs, paying special attention to risk management, notably risk attitude and risk-sharing, and introducing trading strategies based on risk parameters. Software agents were developed using a goal-based architecture in the Java programming language and the JADE multi-agent platform [32, 33]. They have goals and beliefs about electricity markets and negotiate according to the alternating offers protocol by sending and receiving messages [34]. This paper extends the work performed in [4, 6–8, 30, 31], by:

1. Formalizing a new type of contract, the RSC, that can be beneficial to mitigate the risk of bilateral contracts, and serve as a form of hedging against spot price volatility;
2. Considering a risk management process where an agent can analyse the risk factors of different trading options, quantify them and then decide the best option;
3. Adapting the von Neumann-Morgenstern expected multi-objective utility function to compute the utility of different electricity markets agents;
4. Formalizing a new concession factor that can deal with the risk attitude of the agents, such as the shared risk of different items and their uncertainty.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents a literature review. Section 3 introduces the negotiation of bilateral contracts in multi-agent systems. Section 4 addresses the key issues of risk management and risk-sharing during the negotiation of RSCs. Section 5 presents case

studies on bilateral contracting involving risk-sharing. Finally, concluding remarks are presented in section 6.

2. Literature review

The literature contains a richness of approaches to deal with risk, typically as part of portfolio management [4, 6, 8], energy management [5, 27, 35], and to deal with the broader issues of negotiation and decision-making under uncertainty [2, 4, 6–8, 18, 23–26, 30, 31, 35–42].

In particular, Ramos *et al.* [2] developed a model to evaluate the optimal hedging strategy of a generation company, which trades electricity in competitive markets considering the spot and the bilateral contracts markets.

Yang *et al.* [18] proposed a scheduling strategy to optimally define the energy delivery plan of wind farms when participating in energy and frequency regulation markets, considering their production uncertainty.

Xiao, AlAshery and Qiao [23] presented a bi-level stochastic optimization model to define the virtual bids of a wind power producer to day-ahead and real-time markets. It uses virtual bidding to surpass the limitations of markets cleared using the locational marginal pricing algorithm by considering bids to several grid buses instead of only its local bus. Considering different degrees of risk-aversion, virtual bidding increases the profit of the wind power producer, which decreases with increasing degrees of risk aversion, such as the CVaR.

Brigatto and Fanzeres [24] presented a novel electricity portfolio allocation methodology to appropriately assemble a portfolio of call/put options, hedging against the price and quantity risk induced by a short position in supply contracts backed by renewable energy sources.

Cheng *et al.* [25] presented a stochastic short-term scheduling model for a Wind-Solar-Hydro Complementary System, which can simultaneously optimize the day-ahead market bidding strategy and the decomposition of daily bilateral contracts.

Xiao *et al.* [26] proposed a stochastic optimization model to define the bids of wind power producers with different risk attitudes. They concluded that risk-neutral and risk-averse producers using CVaR have the highest expected profit. However, the risk-seeking producer using a new metric, the value at the best scenarios, has both the highest and lowest profit in the case of the best or worst scenarios, respectively. Furthermore, it also has the highest value at the best scenarios and the lowest VaR.

Nojavan *et al.* [35] modelled the attitude towards risk of retailers, and their respective wholesale market behaviour with the main goal of minimizing their costs. They used forward contracts and demand-response programs as risk hedging against spot prices volatility. They concluded that risk-averse retailers replace the energy acquired from the day-ahead market by forward contracts, as a risk mitigation measure.

Khatib *et al.* [36] developed an iterative method where a producer and a consumer can negotiate a bilateral contract described by its time of delivery, duration, amount, and price. This approach allows the negotiating parties to self-specify their risk measures, computing the VaR, and through a probability distribution, each party can self-specify how the uncertain parameters such as spot price, fuel price and demand shall be modelled. Caruso *et al.* [37] also use the VaR to measure risk, but place greater emphasis on the producer, who has to make decisions about bidding on the spot market or signing bilateral contracts.

Guesmi *et al.* [38] presented a model that deals with the minimization of the price risk that retailers have on wholesale markets. The main goal of this model consists of increasing the return of retailers and minimizing their price risk by considering forward contracts, self-generating facilities, and call or put options, besides the day-ahead market.

Karandikar *et al.* [39] quantified risk using the “Risk Adjustment Recovery on Capital”. Considering an elastic load, to guarantee the retailers risk-constrained pay-off, they use a strategic assessment of the acquisition of bilateral contracts that selects the best quantity of power acquired through bilateral contracts considering the market prices of day-ahead markets.

Jean-Paul *et al.* [40] presented a study indicating that the effect of the socio-demographic diversity of residential consumers can affect the financial risk of retailers, because of the quantity risk of the consumers. They concluded that retailers shall consider a portfolio of consumers with a total covariance close to zero, to decrease their financial risk.

Faia *et al.* [41] presented a model for traders that maximizes their return based on their risk preference.

Sun *et al.* [42] used the CVaR in the risk assessment phase to maximize the profit of retailers. They select the best options of wholesale markets to buy electricity, and feed their portfolios of consumers considering tariffs with time-of-use or real-time pricing rates. They concluded that while risk-averse retailers tend to trade in the long-term, risk-seeking retailers prefer trading in the short-term.

Concerning the author's relevant pieces of work, a discussion follows. In [30] it was concluded that by negotiating the shared risk of forward contracts, both parties can sign more beneficial contracts. In [7] it was verified that usually sellers face more risks than buyers when signing a forward contract, which make them require a higher risk premium when negotiating the price of electricity. In [8] it was concluded that risk-seeking retailers may obtain higher outputs from retail markets than risk-averse retailers, because high variations in return lead to small variations in risk. The work presented in [31] focused on bilateral contracting involving contracts for difference (CfDs), also known as swaps, presenting the different risk attitudes of agents. A case study illustrated how parties can negotiate a CfD and how the compensation scheme works. In [6] it was verified that for a given target return, risk-seeking retailers compute more competitive tariffs, attracting more consumers to their portfolios. However, risk-averse retailers have more stable portfolios, obtaining higher outputs in both favourable and unfavourable situations. In [4] it was presented a multi-objective risk-return optimization to obtain the optimal set of market products where retailers shall participate. It concluded that retailers increase their return from markets by participating in derivatives market. However, these markets are speculative, so the potential losses that risk-neutral retailers face may be higher than their potential returns.

3. Bilateral Contracting in Multi-agent Systems

Bilateral contracts can follow the form of physical or financial contracts and are normally negotiated from years to a day before their delivery. Normally they need to include the starting and ending dates and times, and the periodic prices and quantities during the contract. In a more general form, the price per period and the traded quantity can be time-varying over the contract duration in the case of non-standard private bilateral contracts. They can be, and typically are, a form of hedging. They are often negotiated in the derivatives market and can take several forms: forwards, futures, options and CfDs. A detailed description of these contracts can be found in [27, 30]. In the case of physical contracts, the system operator checks for the feasibility of the agreement, communicating it to the market operator, which informs players about the ratification or not of the contract. The transactions using forward contracts are performed assuming their liquidation, *i.e.*, the seller delivers the product and the buyer pays its price in a future date.

Normally, CfDs, futures and options are used as financial instruments to hedge against the volatility of spot prices [43]. In CFDs, you have to negotiate the strike price and quantity of the contract during its duration. Thus, agents have to receive or pay the difference between that price and the market price during that period, considering if they are in the buyer or seller positions. Futures and options can also be used as physical contracts, being that physical quantity obtained through spot markets. Using these contracts is possible to sign a contract for a future date, defining a present value for the strike price and quantity of electricity. The main difference between them is that using futures the financial transaction has to be accomplished in the future date, and using options the agent that is in the buyer position pays a negotiated price (fee) when signs the contract and then in the future date has the option to accomplish or not the transaction, known as the call option (the seller has to follow the buyer's desire). On the contrary, using a put option, the seller, by paying a specific price to the buyer, has the option to accomplish or not the transaction.

To effectively manage risk, it is important to model several factors and processes associated with the potential risks that players may be exposed in the transactions [27]. Software agents may help to manage both the complexity of centralized markets and the challenges of bilateral contracting of electricity. They can exhibit a goal-oriented behaviour, respond to changes that occur in the marketplace in which they operate, and reach mutually acceptable agreements through negotiation. In particular, agents are broadly classified into risk-averse ($\lambda > 0$), risk neutral ($\lambda = 0$), and risk-seeking ($\lambda < 0$), where λ is a risk preference parameter or the risk attitude.

3.1. Risk Preferences

Software agents, on behalf of market players, are exposed to risks associated with price volatility, and uncertainties regarding supply and demand. Considering their attitude towards risk, the agents fit into one of the following categories:

1. *Risk-averse*: prefer a setting where they have a guaranteed profit, to another setting where that profit can be higher but riskier, so, there is a chance of not getting anything or even losing the investment;
2. *Risk-seeking*: prefer a setting where there is a chance of making higher profits (although they are not guaranteed);
3. *Risk-neutral*: normally neglect risk, and tries to maximize profit.

Consequently, risk-averse agents normally accept profits somewhat worse than they can get later in exchange for the security of getting fixed profits now. Instead, risk-seeking agents feel free to take a substantial risk to expect higher profits.

3.2. Decision-making under uncertainty

Considering negotiation and decision-making under uncertainty, when scoring contracts the preferences of agents can be represented using an additive function $U(\mathbf{x})$ with different properties [44]. Considering the utility independence, the additive function can be written as follows:

$$U(\mathbf{x}) = \pi_1 v(x_1) + \pi_2 v(x_2) \cdots + \pi_n v(x_n) \quad (1)$$

Considering choice under uncertainty, this particular form of the additive function can be written as a weighted sum of some (marginal) utility functions $v(x_1), \dots, v(x_n)$, of the outcome level on each issue x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , where the weights are given by the probabilities π_1, \dots, π_n . The risk preference can be modelled by considering the adaptation of a von Neumann-Morgenstern expected multi-objective utility function to electricity trading [45]. Each agent can have a set of objectives (e.g., maximizing profits, minimizing costs, maximizing market share, maximizing capacity utilization, minimizing unserved energy, etc.). Diverse types of agents have different types of objectives. Normally, a seller agent has the objective of maximizing profits and the buyer agent has the objective of minimizing costs. The von Neumann-Morgenstern utility function have been adapted to deal with the shared risk of diverse items and its illustration follows.

Let $U_{s,n}(p_{n,1}, \dots, p_{n,k})$ be the seller overall expected utility function. The Von Neumann-Morgenstern expected multi-objective utility function $v_{s,k}$ of a seller agent $a_j \in \mathcal{A}$ takes the form:

$$v_{s,k}(p_{n,k}, \beta_i, \sigma_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{1 - e^{\left(\lambda \times \frac{(p_{n,k} - X_{n,min} - \sum_{i=0}^I (1 - \beta_i) \sigma_i)}{(X_{n,max} - X_{n,min} - \sum_{i=0}^I (1 - \beta_i) \sigma_i)} \right)}}{1 - e^\lambda}, & \text{for } \lambda \neq 0 \\ \frac{(p_{n,k} - X_{n,min} - \sum_{i=0}^I (1 - \beta_i) \sigma_i)}{(X_{n,max} - X_{n,min} - \sum_{i=0}^I (1 - \beta_i) \sigma_i)}, & \text{for } \lambda = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Similarly, a multi-objective decreasing utility function is defined for the

buyer agent by:

$$v_{b,k}(p_{n,k}, \beta_i, \sigma_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{1-e^{\left(\lambda \times \frac{(X_{n,max}-p_{n,k}-\sum_{i=0}^I \beta_i \sigma_i)}{(X_{n,max}-X_{n,min}-\sum_{i=0}^I \beta_i \sigma_i)}\right)}}{1-e^\lambda}, & \text{for } \lambda \neq 0 \\ \frac{(X_{n,max}-p_{n,k}-\sum_{i=0}^I \beta_i \sigma_i)}{(X_{n,max}-X_{n,min}-\sum_{i=0}^I \beta_i \sigma_i)}, & \text{for } \lambda = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where:

- (i) $p_{n,k}$ is the offer or counter-offer price of issue n in the proposal k ;
- (ii) λ is the risk preference;
- (iii) $X_{n,min}$ and $X_{n,max}$ are the minimum and maximum expected values.
- (iv) $\beta_0 \in [0, 1]$ is a risk-sharing parameter indexed to the negotiated item's market price;
- (v) $\beta_i \in [0, 1]$ are the risk-sharing parameters associated to the shared risk of each item's i market price;
- (vi) σ_i quantifies the uncertainties related to the future price of each item;

The risk preference λ are personalized to each agent. The minimum and maximum expected values $X_{n,min}$ and $X_{n,max}$, and the uncertainties σ_i (using different metrics as VaR and CVaR), are computed by each agent, so their values may differ. For illustrative purposes, it is presented an example describing how buyer agents can trade energy in a liberalized market, involving both a spot market and forward bilateral contracts, considering an item with a single issue (price). *E.g.*, consider a buyer agent a_b trading power either through bilateral contracts and from the day-ahead market. One of the objectives of a_b is to minimize the cost of electricity. Its utility increases for decreasing values of cost. For a given price p_k of a bilateral contract, the utility of a risk-seeking agent, $U_{0,b,n}$, is higher than the one of a risk-averse agent, $U_{2,b,n}$ (see Fig. 1). If the maximum reference cost of energy, X_{max} , of a_b is higher than its buying price p_k , then for lower prices, a_b 's cost is lower and consequently, the utility will be higher. Hence, under similar circumstances, a risk-averse agent may not change its strategy to buy energy, while a risk-seeking agent may not be satisfied with the low value of the utility and may try to increase it by shifting some quantity of energy from the bilateral market to the spot market.

Figure 1: Risk attitude and utility of a buyer agent.

One of the key aspects of bilateral negotiation is the adoption of a negotiation protocol that settles the rules of trading. Has been considered an alternating offers protocol [34]. A definition of a negotiation strategy can be found in [46]. For bilateral contracting in electricity markets, can be used strategies that consider the quantity and price of energy for different trading periods [47]. A different criterion was introduced in [30], namely the attitude towards risk. This work considers different criteria related to risk management, namely risk attitude and risk-sharing (see next section).

4. Risk Management and Sharing in Bilateral Contracts

Systematically, risk management can be divided into three phases: (i) risk assessment, (ii) characterization, and (iii) hedging [29]. In the first phase, it is important to analyse the price fluctuations of the raw materials (natural gas, crude oil, coal, etc.) and the weather variability (wind speed, solar irradiance, etc.) that shall be required to produce electricity. In a second stage shall be verified the different types of markets where is possible to trade energy, physically (spot, over-the-counter and forward) and financially (derivatives) and analyse them in terms of dynamics and risk, such as the other raw materials markets [27]. At this phase, it is also important to check all types of consumers of this market, analysing their activity, financial status and consumption pattern. In the third phase, traders shall define the set of

market products used to trade energy.

For risk-averse agents, risk-sharing is a good choice as a risk mitigation measure [7, 31]. Risk-sharing, also known as “risk distribution”, is a risk hedging method in which the premiums and losses in risk are distributed among several participants. *E.g.*, it can be used as a self-insurance method of managing or reducing exposure to risk by spreading the problem of loss among several entities. This paper addresses the benefit of sharing some of the risks with the opponent. While negotiating a medium or long-term forward contract (a physical contract with fixed price), the risk exposure of a seller concerning the price is very high because the seller is engaging to deliver the negotiated quantity of the item at a fixed price for several months, but the production or acquisition price of the item can suffer several changes during the contract length [7, 14]. In a forward contract how longer is the contract length higher will be the risk exposure of the seller. Also, how higher is the seller risk exposure, higher will be the risk premium requested by the seller [7, 8]. Furthermore, in CfDs, futures and options contracts, how longer is the contract length higher will be the risk exposure of the agents. All these contracts are standardized and have significant exposure to market prices. So, other solutions shall be considered to reduce the premium that the seller requires when selling an item. Thus, sellers can negotiate private bilateral contracts with buyers in the non-organized market, using a non-standardized type of contract where they can share their future risks with the buyer, which is risk-sharing.

4.1. Risk-Sharing Contract

Exist several risks when a seller agent has to comply with a signed contract, providing to customers the final product agreed in the deal. In an organization, the risks can be classified by their: (i) occurring likelihood and severity or magnitude (low or high likelihood and low or high magnitude), (ii) temporality (short-term and medium or long-term risks), (iii) hazard (extreme events that the agent does not want to happen), (iv) uncertainties (the costs that will be included but will vary), (v) opportunities (the benefits that the agent is seeking), and (vi) typology (market, operation, credit, legal, counter-party and liquidity risks, etc.) [29]. Some of these risks like operation and credit risks can be avoided by the acquisition of insurances, which will increase the item’s price. Other risks like market risks (risks of the item or the required raw materials to produce that item, like an increase or decrease in the item’s price) can be shared with customers in a bilateral contract.

This article aims to demonstrate that if sellers share part of their market risks with buyers, they can achieve a mutually beneficial deal (better prices and less risk). Depending on the sellers' risk-sharing magnitude, sellers will decrease their required risk premium and offer better prices to buyers. The sellers' shared risk can be negotiated by the parties and must be indexed to specific market indexes. So, this shared risk can be considered a price market-based shared risk. Also, buyers shall share their risks. For example, an industrial company very dependent on specific raw materials subject to market price variation over time, can share their price risk. If it negotiates long-term electricity standardized contracts, and the raw materials price increases substantially, it can have liquidity problems and in the end, it does not have enough money to pay for goods like electricity. So, it has market risks and liquidity risks. To decrease these risks the buyer can also share its main risks, like the raw material price (market-risk) with the electricity seller, obtaining a tariff discount when the raw material price increases, and a tariff increase when it decreases (in the case of a two-way compensation). This kind of long-term contract negotiation with risk-sharing may decrease some of the short and long-term risk exposure of both agents, and increase the relationship and benefit between them. By negotiating this kind of contract all agents can increase their return/risk ratio. Producers can decrease their market risk and operational exposure to electricity and raw materials prices, and also to liquidity risks (if they signed several physical long-term bilateral contracts and the electricity and raw materials start increasing their prices). Also, commercial agents like traders and retailers can benefit from this type of contract by reducing their exposure to electricity prices and liquidity risks. Consumers can obtain more competitive tariffs from sellers (by decreasing their risks, sellers can decrease their required risk premium), decreasing their (expected) costs with electricity. Although, they increase their exposure to the market prices volatility (comparing with all contracts except CfDs), increasing the risks over their tariffs.

Actual market designs and products do not incentive the active participation of VRES without incentives, because of the continuous price depressing with increasing levels of VRES [12]. Currently, governments incentive the investment in new mature renewable technologies with capacity auctions based on CfDs, being the remuneration dependent of market prices, or power purchase agreements for long-time periods (normally more than 15 years), guaranteeing a fixed remuneration per unit of produced energy during that period, independently of market prices [11]. These incentives

are important in the case of projects that require credit, because they give the financial stability that financial institutions need to provide credit, but they do not reflect the long-term variability of market prices. Such long-term contracts can be very risky to governments, but agreements considering the shared risk of market prices can be used as risk hedging in future contracts with renewable technologies. So, the International Energy Agency is against this kind of incentives because they are discriminatory (only for renewable technologies), and affect the free fluctuation of prices, discouraging competition [48]. The consequences of these incentives are an increase in the incidence of negative prices in wholesale markets, and an increase in the difference between wholesale and retail prices [3, 13]. Currently, in Europe, the wholesale price of electrical energy only weighs around 37% of the retail price, mainly because of all negative externalities, such as economic incentives to producers, which originated an over-cost charged to consumers [6]. Against this background, the use of a RSC, as risk mitigation of the volatility of the wholesale price of electrical energy is appropriated for long-term bilateral agreements.

In Figure 2 can be seen the main characteristics of the RSC, such as the essential variables that have to be negotiated and/or agreed and presented in the contract. The RSC can be divided into a standardized contract that can be obtained through a derivatives exchange or a non-standardized contract that has to be negotiated privately (see Figure 3). The standard RSC is the simplest version and can be purchased as a product like options, but not continuously as futures or CfDs in the derivatives exchange. Considering the future price of the item in the stock exchange, different sets of strike prices and risk-sharing values can be proposed. How better is the strike price (concerning the indexed market price) higher will be the risk shared, and vice versa. Also, the quantity of the item that can be contracted is fixed (in the case of electricity is 0.1 or 1 MWh), but it can be acquired through multiple contracts. Different sets of strike prices and risk-shared values are available to be acquired, considering the agent position as buyer or seller. The non-standardized RSC has to be negotiated privately between a seller and a buyer. Its advantage consists in the shared risk of diverse items, different from the item under negotiation. The features of the contract that can be negotiated are: i) the indexed items to be risk shared, ii) their strike prices, iii) the magnitude of the shared risk, iv) the type of sharing, and v) the compensation type and seasonality.

Several types of items can be associated for risk-sharing in this type

Figure 2: The characteristics of the Risk-Sharing contract.

Figure 3: The characteristics of the standard and non-standard RSC.

of contract. Although, sharing the risks of the negotiated item is more common. Thus, sharing the risk associated with other items related (or not) to the negotiated item can also be proposed. For example, considering that electricity is the negotiated item we can associate natural gas, coal or fuel oil as important items to produce electricity, and the renewables penetration in the market, as an important characteristic that affects the market prices.

4.1.1. Market-based risk-sharing of the item's price

This type of risk-sharing shall be indexed to the market of the negotiated item, like in CfDs. In CfDs and futures, both agents have full exposure to market prices, in the other types of contracts mentioned before, only the seller has full exposure to market prices, but in the RSC they can negotiate the shared risk associated with the negotiated item.

4.1.2. Market-based risk-sharing of the prices of diverse items

To negotiate this type of risk-sharing, the agents must specify from which type of items/raw materials they want to share their risks, and to which market that item will be indexed. The strike price of that item shall be the price at the indexed market where they sign the contract. If there are some raw materials that cannot have the same metric (*e.g.*, for electricity (€/MWh)) the risk-sharing can be negotiated as a percentage. *E.g.*, a buyer's shared risk of 10% considering the raw material market price (*e.g.*, €/ton) at a maximum of 10% increase/decrease. If it varies 10%, -20% and 120% concerning the defined strike price, the electricity price charged by the seller will have a variation of -1%, 2% and -10%, respectively, in a two-way compensation, or -1%, 0% and -10%, when only the buyer is compensated.

Returning to previous example, considering that the seller shares the price risk associated with a specific raw material (item 2) with the same metric of the negotiated item, considering a strike price of 50 mu (Month 0), and the buyer also shares a raw material's (item 3) risk but with a different metric and a strike price of 100 mu² ("2" because the metric is different). They negotiate the shared risk of those raw materials and both agree that the seller shares 20% of the price risk of item 2 (two-way risk-sharing), and the buyer has a maximum of 10% discount if the prices of item 3 start rising (one-way risk-sharing). If in Month 1 the market price of item 2 is 55 mu, in Month 3 is 45 mu, and in the other months is 50 mu. In Month 1 the charged price will increase in 1 mu, in Month 3 it will decrease in 1 mu, and in the other months it will not have any difference (two-way compensation). Similarly, if

the price of item 3 in Month 1 is 90 mu2, in Months 2, 4 and 5 is 100 mu2, and in Month 3 is 110 mu2, the seller will give 1% discount to the item's strike price only in Month 3 (one-way compensation). Concluding, they negotiate the strike price of item 1 as 100 mu, but because they shared the risk of the other two items, the charged price will be 103.5 (100+2.5+1), 100.0, 99.5 (100*(100%-10%*(110-100))), 94 (100-5-1) and 100 mu in Months 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5, respectively. The seller has a benefit of 2 mu by negotiating this type of contract when comparing to the spot price, and a loss of 3 mu concerning a forward contract. The buyer has a benefit of 3 mu when comparing to a forward contract, and a loss of 2 mu concerning the spot price (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Compensations of the negotiated item spot price volatility and also the items 2 (shared by the seller) and 3 (shared by the buyer) price volatility.

The risk can be shared by both, when both parties share their risks, or just by one of the parties, when only one of the parties share its risks.

4.1.3. One-way risk-sharing

In this case only one of the parties wants to share its risks. In any investment every agent wants a certain quantity of return that considers the risk-free investments (deposits with about a certain percentage of return) plus the risk premium (will be higher how higher are the investment risks, such as price, volumes, credit, liquidity, etc.). Producers have risks mainly in the prices of raw materials, as they fluctuate over time. How higher the

duration of their contracts, higher are their risks and risk premiums requested for their investment in the required raw materials to produce the electricity demanded by consumers. So, to reduce the risk premium those producers require, they can share their risks when investing in raw materials by sharing the risks associated with the raw material acquisition (prices volatility) with consumers. Thus, they can reduce their risk and requested return, reducing the price proposed to consumers. If the agent is an industrial consumer, its shared risk can be indexed to raw material with great importance to its industrial process because a substantial increase in its price can originate liquidity risks.

4.1.4. Two-way risk-sharing

This is a good option when both parties want to decrease the magnitude effect of future risks. This can be associated with a problem-solving strategy, where both parties care about each other and want to achieve a mutually beneficial deal. This is the case of the example presented in Figure 4, where the seller shares its risks associated with the price volatility of items 1 and 2, and the buyer did the same with item 3. The type of compensation also has to be chosen considering that only one or both parties are compensated.

4.1.5. One-way compensation

This is the case where just one of the parties is compensated. If it is the seller who is compensated, only when the market price of the item is higher than the reference price the buyer will have to compensate the seller, and when it is lower there is no compensation to the buyer. In the opposite case, when is the buyer who is compensated, just when the market price of the item is lower than the reference price the seller will compensate the buyer, on the contrary, the buyer will not compensate the seller (the case of Figure 4 concerning item 3). Shall be considered that the strike price (negotiated price) can be different from the reference price (market current price) due to several factors, especially the uncertainty concerning future prices. This type of clause is used by the negotiated contracts between the United Kingdom government and the electricity producers with power plants that use renewable sources [49]. They negotiate specific CfDs with a fixed strike price, and when the electricity price is lower the government has to compensate the producers (paying the strike price), otherwise, there is no compensation.

4.1.6. Two-way compensation

Using a two-way compensation, both parties have to compensate each other, depending on the shared risk of the items they share, and on their price fluctuations in the indexed markets. The seasonality of the compensation also has to be described in the contract, and in general can follow these two forms: compensation at the end of the contract or seasonal compensation.

4.1.7. Compensation at the end of contract

Considering the type of sharing and compensation signed in the contract, in the end of the contract the parties have to check if there will be a compensation and make that transaction (common in short-term contracts).

4.1.8. Seasonal compensation

Both parties have to agree with the seasonality of the compensation, and compute and transact the compensation at the defined seasonality (more used in long-term contracts). In the case of the previous example the compensation is monthly (see Figure 4).

4.1.9. Compensation scheme

The compensation scheme used to compute the RSC price, $p_{RSC,t,p}$, and the total cost/revenue of the RSC can follow several formulations, depending if it is seasonal or not, and on the agent's point of view (seller or buyer). For a seller agent with seasonal compensation, the formulation is:

$$p_{RSC,t,p}^{seller} = -sp_p + \sum_{i=0}^I \min(\beta_i (rp_{i,p} - \overline{cp_{i,t,p}}), \max_{i,p}) \quad (4)$$

$$\Pi_{RSC,T} = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{p=1}^P q_{t,p} \times p_{RSC,t,p}^{seller} \quad (5)$$

where:

- (i) $p_{RSC,t,p}^{seller}$ is the RSC price computed by the seller for period p (peak, off-peak, etc.) of time horizon t (time horizon of the compensation);
- (ii) sp_p is the negotiated strike price for period p ;
- (iii) β_i is the negotiated risk-sharing parameter for item i ;
- (iv) $rp_{i,p}$ is the reference price defined in the contract for item i at period p ;

- (v) $\overline{cp_{i,t,p}}$ is the arithmetic average of the market clearing price for item i , at period p of time horizon t . In the case of any imposed limit to the maximum compensation, it is considered ∞ ;
- (vi) $\Pi_{RSC,T}$ is the revenue of the RSC during the whole contract duration, T ;
- (vii) $q_{t,p}$ is the total quantity traded.

Using this formulation, it is possible to compute the entire compensation of the contract, from $t = 1$ to T , or seasonally, step by step ($t = 1, t = 2$, etc.). This result is also from the point of view of the seller. Exactly the opposite value has to be computed by the buyer.

The arithmetic average clearing price, $\overline{cp_{i,t,p}}$, of the item, i , is computed considering its market prices, $p_{i,p,h}$, and traded quantities of electricity, $q_{p,h}^{spot}$, of each market clearing, h , during the number of clearing periods, H , of each item's period p , as follows:

$$\overline{cp_{i,t,p}} = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^H p_{i,p,h} q_{p,h}^{spot}}{\sum_{h=1}^H q_{p,h}^{spot}} \quad (6)$$

In the case of standard contracts, the quantity is fixed per period, so it is considered only the average value of the clearing prices per period.

4.2. Characteristics of standard contracts

Standard contracts only allow trading specific quantities of energy, the tick, normally between 0.1–1 MWh, so they are not subject to quantity risk. If the parties want to trade higher quantities of energy in the derivative exchanges, they have to trade multiple contracts. Table 1 presents the main characteristics of the standard contracts presented in the derivatives markets, and of the proposed standard version of the RSC [27].

Analysing the table is possible to verify that the CfD is the only type of contract that does not allow the physical settlement, and forward contracts are the only type of contracts that are not affected by future changes in the market prices. These contracts have significant differences in their price risk. While in CfDs and futures, both agents have the same degree of risk. In forward contracts both parties settled the agreed price, equal during the contract duration. So, while buyers pay a fixed price during the contract, sellers may have to guarantee the energy independently of the future market

Table 1: Main characteristics of standard contracts.

Contracts	Physical	Financial	Price Risk	Indexed	Compensation
CfDs	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Forward	Yes	Yes	Seller	No	No
Futures	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Options	Yes	Yes	Options' sellers	Yes	Yes
RSC	Yes	Yes	Shared	Yes	Yes

prices of it. In forward contracts the risk asymmetry between sellers and buyers is significant, since sellers face almost all price and quantity risks [7]. Concerning option contracts, the agent that buys the option have the right but not the obligation to exercise it. On the contrary, the agent who sells the option receive a fee but then are exposed to the future price risk of markets. In a standard RSC both agents are exposed to the spot index. So, during the contract they are exposed to the market volatility of spot markets. The degree of exposure is given by the risk shared, β . While in futures and CFDs both agents have total exposure to the spot index, by using standard RSCs their exposure is reduced by the risk shared value. Considering forwards and options contracts, both the sellers of energy and options will face almost all price risk, requesting a substantial risk-premium and fee to trade these contracts, respectively. Against this background, standard RSCs have less risk exposure to the volatility of spot prices than futures and CfDs. Furthermore, they allow negotiating more competitive prices, levelling the risk exposure of both parties concerning forwards and options contracts. This type of contract is irreplaceable since even with the multiple acquisitions of (other) several derivative contracts, it is almost impossible to replicate the RSC contract without knowing the future price of electricity.

Next, it is presented a negotiation strategy that can deal with risk, depending on the risk attitude and risk-sharing.

4.3. Negotiation strategy to deal with risk-sharing

In this section it is defined a negotiation strategy that deals with the RSC. Considering the degree of shared risk that an agent transfer or receive from the opponent, the concession level to achieve an agreement differs.

For a seller agent a_s , the price is controlled by a risk management concession factor, defined by the following function:

$$C_f(\lambda, \beta_i, \sigma_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{C - e^{\ln(C)\lambda \left(1 + \frac{-\lambda + \|\lambda\|}{2\lambda} - \frac{\lambda}{\|\lambda\|} \frac{\sum_{i=0}^I \beta_i \sigma_i}{\sum_{i=0}^I \sigma_i}\right)}}{1 - e^\lambda}, & \text{for } \lambda \neq 0 \\ C_{f_N} = C/2, & \text{for } \lambda = 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Similarly, the concession factor for a buyer agent a_b is defined as follows:

$$C_f(\lambda, \beta_i, \sigma_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{C - e^{\ln(C)\lambda \left(1 - \frac{\lambda + \|\lambda\|}{2\lambda} + \frac{\lambda}{\|\lambda\|} \frac{\sum_{i=0}^I \beta_i \sigma_i}{\sum_{i=0}^I \sigma_i}\right)}}{1 - e^\lambda}, & \text{for } \lambda \neq 0 \\ C_{f_N} = C/2, & \text{for } \lambda = 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $C \in [0; 1]$ is the maximum concession factor and C_{f_N} is the risk-neutral concession factor (see also Fig. 5 and Fig. 6).

Figure 5: Concession factor considering the risk attitude of the seller, and the contract's shared risk.

E.g., consider a buyer agent a_b negotiating a bilateral contract with a seller agent a_s to buy electricity. If a_b is a risk-averse agent, it does not want to be exposed to a_s 's potential risks. Hence, for a fixed price and a lower shared risk β of a_s , then a_b 's utility will be higher, and consequently to conclude the deal a_b will tend to adopt a soft attitude in negotiation (higher

Figure 6: Concession factor considering the risk attitude of the buyer, and the contract's shared risk.

concession factor). Conversely, how higher is the shared risk of a_s , lower will be a_b 's utility, leading this agent to adopt a tough position in negotiation. If a_b is a risk-seeking agent, it wants some/more exposure to a_s 's potential risks, and thus its negotiation attitude shall be the opposite of the aforementioned attitudes of a risk-averse agent. Concluding, if the buyer is a risk-averse agent, it prefers higher prices than a high exposition to the seller's potential risks. Otherwise, if it is a risk-seeking agent, to negotiate better prices, it prefers a higher exposition to the seller's potential risks (see Figures 5 and 6).

4.4. Metrics of market performance

To evaluate the different outputs of the market choices of each agent, it is important to define metrics to compute the cost and profit with electricity trading. Considering producers, for a given time horizon, T , their profit, Π_T , from wholesale markets can be computed considering the quantity of energy they sell at spot markets, q_p^{spot} , and through each type, o , of bilateral contract, $q_{o,p}$, but also considering their penalties with imbalances, as follows:

$$\Pi_T = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{p=1}^P (p_{t,p}^{spot} - c_{t,p}) \times q_{t,p}^{spot} + p_{t,p}^{imb} |q_{t,p}^{imb}| + \sum_{o=1}^O (p_{o,t,p} - c_{t,p}) \times q_{o,t,p} \quad (9)$$

$$q_{t,p}^{imb} = q_{t,p}^{inj} - q_{t,p}^{spot} - \sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t,p} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{cases} p_{t,p}^{imb} = p_{up,t,p}, & \text{for } q_{t,p}^{imb} > 0 \\ p_{t,p}^{imb} = p_{down,t,p}, & \text{for } q_{t,p}^{imb} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where during period p of time horizon t :

- (i) $p_{t,p}^{spot}$ is the spot price;
- (ii) $c_{t,p}$ is the marginal cost to produce energy;
- (iii) $p_{o,t,p}$ is the price defined/computed in the bilateral contract, o ;
- (iv) $q_{t,p}^{imb}$ is the imbalanced quantity from the programmed dispatch;
- (v) $q_{t,p}^{inj}$ is the injected quantity;
- (vi) $p_{t,p}^{imb}$ is the imbalances price;
- (vii) $p_{up,t,p}$ is the up imbalances price;
- (viii) $p_{down,t,p}$ is the down imbalances price;

The formulation used to compute the final price, $p_{o,t,p}$, of all standard derivatives products can be found in [4, 31] with the exception of the RSC, which can be found in Equation 4.

Normally, imbalance prices consider dual pricing, being positive in the case of upward deviations, and negative otherwise. [17]. Imbalance prices are computed according to the penalties obtained from the costs in the balancing markets. Penalties can consider single or dual pricing. Single pricing passes the total balancing costs to the Balance Responsible Parties (BRPs). Dual pricing considers that downward BRPs only pay the upward balance costs, and upward BRPs only receive the downward balance costs. Sometimes, deviations can be positive for the system according to the results of the balancing markets. When the prices of balancing markets are more competitive than the prices of spot markets, penalties can be positive, and the BRPs receive an extra money from their deviations. In the case of consumers and retailers, it is possible to compute the cost, Γ_T , with electricity, as follows:

$$\Gamma_T = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{p=1}^P p_{t,p}^{spot} q_{t,p}^{spot} + p_{t,p}^{imb} |q_{t,p}^{imb}| + \sum_{o=1}^O p_{o,t,p} q_{o,t,p} \quad (12)$$

$$q_{t,p}^{imb} = q_{t,p}^{spot} - q_{t,p}^{con} + \sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t,p} \quad (13)$$

where $q_{t,p}^{con}$ is the consumed quantity during period p of time horizon t .

5. Case studies on bilateral negotiation of Risk-Sharing Contracts

The first case study investigates the benefit of RSCs from the point of view of variable generation and retailers, players that face price and quantity uncertainty at spot markets. The second case study simulates the negotiation of a private RSC between a traditional producer and a big consumer, players that mainly face the price uncertainty of commodities.

5.1. Case study I - Negotiation between a wind farms aggregator and a retailer

Consider a hypothetical scenario where a wind farms aggregator, an aggregator software agent, attracts wind farms to its portfolio after the end of their governmental incentives. Currently, it has a set of real wind farms from the centre of Portugal in its portfolio, with 249 MW of installed capacity. It can sell the wind farms production at spot markets of the Iberian Electricity Market (MIBEL), facing the quantity and price risks of its clients, or negotiating bilateral contracts with other players. MIBEL is composed of Portugal and Spain, and includes a day-ahead market (DAM) and an intra-day market managed by the Spanish electricity market operator (OMIE), and a derivatives market managed by the Portuguese electricity market operator (OMIP).

A retailer software agent, representing a real electricity retail company, intends to negotiate a bilateral contract with the wind farms aggregator. It can buy the energy requested by its clients from spot markets, facing price and quantity uncertainty, but it has the goals of purchasing renewable energy with guarantees of origin, and reduce its costs with deviation penalties, proposing “green” tariffs, considering 100% renewable energy, to its clients.

Against this background, these players have the following set of options to trade energy:

1. Day-ahead and intraday markets (spot): submit bids to the spot markets;
2. Forward Contract: negotiate a physical bilateral contract;
3. Standard Risk-Sharing Contract: negotiate a physical standardized RSC;
4. Risk-Sharing Contract: negotiate a private non-standard physical bilateral contract with risk-sharing;

Using real data from the wind power forecasts and their observed production, such as real data from the retail company deviations in 2010¹, it is possible to compute the output of these players while bidding at spot markets or negotiating bilateral contracts. The wind aggregator negotiated the 249 MW of its wind farms portfolio with the retailer. In the case of standard contracts, they negotiated a strike price equal to 36 €/MWh, being the wind aggregator responsible for supplying that quantity of energy, and for its deviations. So, in the second and third options in the case of producing below 249 MW, the wind aggregator will buy the remaining energy from spot markets and will pay penalties for its deviations. Considering RSCs, they agreed with a 50% share over the day-ahead market (DAM) price. So, when the DAM price is higher than the strike price, the retailer compensates the wind aggregator with 50% of the difference, otherwise it is the wind aggregator that compensates the retailer. In the case of a private RSC, the retailer is responsible for all the wind aggregator production and deviations. So, they negotiate a strike price equal to 26 €/MWh. Table 2 presents each option output from the point of view of the wind aggregator.

In 2010 the average market value was 37.20 €/MWh. So, the wind aggregator (can be) losing money in the case of not participating at spot markets, considering the standard contracts with a strike price of 36 €/MWh. By signing a standard RSC the wind aggregator is hedging against a possible fall in the day-ahead prices, receiving less money in the case of a rise in these prices when compared to trading on the day-ahead market, but losing less money concerning a forward contract. Typically, wind farms produce more during the night, when the prices are lower. So, in 2010, the market value of the energy traded by the wind aggregator was 32.55 €/MWh. Considering

¹This data is available in the Portuguese transmission system operator page about the imbalances per market Agent (see <https://www.mercado.ren.pt/EN/Electr/MarketInfo/MarketResults/Imbalances/Pages/ImbalancesAgent.aspx>)

Table 2: The profit of the wind aggregator from each option, and the difference with the spot market profit.

	Spot	Forward	Standard RSC	RSC
Profit (€/MWh)	28.60	24.43	26.51	29.27
Spot Difference (%)	0.00	-14.58	-7.85	2.36

the non-standard RSC contract with a strike price of 26 €/MWh and a 50% share of the day-ahead price risk, the wind aggregator receives 29.27 €/MWh, which is a good deal. The negotiation of a private RSC conducts the wind aggregator to a situation where it is only subject to price risk, hedging against it and passing its responsibilities as a BRP to the retailer, eliminating its quantity and deviation risks.

Only considering the hourly quantity (249 MWh) that the retailer is trading with the wind aggregator, if it buys it from the day-ahead market it costs 37.20 €/MWh. By signing forward contracts, buyers will not face any risk, because they buy that quantity of energy for a fixed price during the contracted period, so they only have the risk of making a bad deal in the case of prices fall. In this forward contract, the retailer pays an hourly value of 36 €/MWh. Comparing with the forward contract, the RSC allows the retailer to hedge against a fall in market prices, reducing its risk of making a bad deal. In this case, market prices are higher than the contract's strike price. So, considering the contracted RSC, the retailer has to compensate the wind aggregator. Considering the real-time deviations that the retailer has with its consumers, such as its responsibility with the wind aggregator deviations, in the case of a non-standard RSC, it is possible to compute the retailer costs with penalties considering these trading options. While the costs and total costs of the retailer are levelized for every unit of consumed energy, the costs with penalties are levelized per unit of unbalanced energy. Table 3 presented the trading cost, penalties and total cost that the retailer has with each option, comparing them with trading only on spot markets.

In the non-standard RSC the retailer will be responsible for the production and deviations of the wind generation. The wind aggregator has a higher production during off-peak periods, so its energy has lower value when comparing to average spot prices. If the retailer trades energy using

Table 3: Trading cost, penalties and total cost of the retailer from each option, and the difference with the spot costs.

	Spot	Forward	Standard RSC	RSC
Cost (€/MWh)	37.20	36.00	36.60	36.07
Penalty (€/MWh)	24.06	24.06	24.06	22.70
Total Cost (€/MWh)	40.93	39.78	40.35	40.44
Spot Difference (%)	0.00	-2.81	-1.40	-1.20

forward contracts, as the strike price is, on average, lower than the day-ahead prices, the retailer can reduce its costs when compared with RSCs.

By trading standard contracts, the retailer continues assuming only its deviations such as in spot markets, paying substantial penalties because of them (24.06 €/MWh on average, around 35% of the day-ahead price). Considering the non-standard RSC, by assuming the wind aggregator deviations, the retailer can compensate its deviations, reducing its payment with penalties by 5.63%. This reduction is only possible because the wind aggregator and the retailer deviations are uncorrelated in the majority of hours, reducing the yearly total amount of deviations of both players by 16.8%, from 638 GWh (78% from the retailer) to 531 GWh. However, by assuming the wind aggregator deviations, the retailer has more deviations. So, even if paying cheaper penalties, the increase in the quantity of deviations, increase the total cost of the non-standard RSC in relation to the other options. In this case, the use of a non-standard RSC contract results in a win-win output for both players. Several studies indicate the benefit of load and VRES aggregation due to their complementarity [16]. Some short-run over-the-counter and peer-to-peer markets can also allow trades between consumers and VRES, but do not solve the lack of financing problem that VRES faces [15, 16, 22]. Non-standard RSC contracts are a long-run solution that can allow investment in new renewable power plants without governmental incentives.

Wind farms shall avoid trading standard contracts, because they consider fixed quantities, while their production is uncertain. They shall sell their

energy to aggregators or big market players, who have enough capability or flexibility to compensate their production uncertainty. Retailers shall seize the opportunity of the production uncertainty of VRES, to establish non-standard RSC contracts with them for competitive prices, obtaining mutual beneficial agreements.

5.2. Case study II - Negotiation between a traditional producer and a big consumer

A producer software agent, owner of a combined cycle gas turbine, is going to negotiate a bilateral contract with a consumer software agent, representing an industrial consumer that works with aluminium. But first the producer is going to analyse the several market options to sell its energy in MIBEL, and select the best set of options. The options are:

1. Day-ahead market (DAM): make bids to the day-ahead market;
2. Forward Contract: negotiate a physical bilateral contract with a buyer;
3. Risk-Sharing Contract: negotiate a physical non-standard bilateral contract with risk-sharing;
4. DAM and CfDs: since CfDs are financial contracts, in this option, the producer has to make bids at the day-ahead market and also hedge against price volatility by selling CfDs;
5. DAM and 50% CfDs: exactly like the previous option but in this case exists a virtual share of 50% in the market price risk (in CfDs is not possible to share only 50% of the price risk).

They can negotiate three types of bilateral contracts, two physicals (forward and RSC) and one financial (CfD). Considering the options where the producer sells energy in the DAM, its remuneration decreases when DAM prices fall. To effectively hedge against a possible decrease in the DAM prices, it has to sell CfDs, being compensated when prices fall and compensating the buyer when they rise. To verify which is the best option to be followed by the producer, it is simulated the negotiation of a bilateral contract in this part of the case study.

The producer and the consumer negotiate a 24h-rate tariff for a contract with a duration of six months. Figures 7 and 8 show the initial offers and the price limits for both agents. Fig. 7 shows the VaR values (computed using the formulation adapted from [8]). Fig. 8 also shows the load profile of the consumer. Those values were selected by looking up to real trading

prices associated with the spot market, approximating the case study to the real world. In particular, market reference prices were obtained by analysing MIBEL in 2012. The minimum producer's prices were then set to these reference prices. Also, some energy quantities were based on real data of industrial consumers from Portugal from 2011 to 2014.²

Figure 7: Initial prices, limits and uncertain (VaR) prices of the producer agent.

Negotiation involves an iterative exchange of offers and counter-offers using an alternating offers protocol as presented in [30, 46]. The agents have a risk-averse attitude and use a starting reasonable and conceding moderately strategy considering a concession rate of 10% [47]. The producer wants to share its risks concerning the electricity and natural gas market prices, and the consumer wants to share its risks concerning the aluminum price. So, the negotiated contract will have a two-way risk-sharing and compensation. They both agree that the electricity shared risk, β_0 , will be 50% and that the aluminum shared risk, β_2 , will be 10%, resulting in a maximum discount of 10% in the electricity tariff (the producer will only compensate the aluminum price rise until the double of the strike price). They also agree that the reference price of every item is the market price of that item when they sign

²This data set can be found in an online repository in <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/ElectricityLoadDiagrams20112014#>

Figure 8: Initial prices, limits and requested energy of the consumer agent.

the contract. Because they do not agree with the natural gas shared risk β_1 value, they will negotiate it together with the tariff. To this end, the producer agent started by proposing 40% of risk-sharing to the consumer, who replied by proposing only 10% of the total price risk.

Figure 9 and Table 4 summarize the results obtained. The agents reach an agreement after the producer sent 4 proposals and the consumer submitted 4 proposals. The producer accepted the consumer's offer with a shared risk β_1 of 21%. The preliminary results allow concluding that the mutual utility of both agents is higher than in previous case studies [47], where risk management and sharing were not considered. Also, the mutual utility is higher than in [30] because of the evolution in the risk-sharing negotiation, rising the importance of the parameter β and these new clauses to bilateral contracts, as a form of hedging against the prices volatility of spot markets and standardized contracts.

Now, considering the real market prices in 2012, will be computed the compensation scheme. The average electricity prices are levelized prices of each month (considers the hourly consumption of the consumer). The electricity (elec. indexed to MIBEL), natural gas (NG indexed to NYMEX) and aluminum (al. indexed to global market) strike prices are 45.32 €/MWh, 9.92 €/MWh and 1.52 €/kg, respectively. In Table 5 is possible to verify how the compensation works from the point of view of the consumer as a buyer

Table 4: Case study final results.

Consumer			Producer		
Proposals	Utility	β_1	Proposals	Utility	β_1
4	0.59	21%	4	0.75	79%

Figure 9: Case study final prices.

of electricity. The potential cost of the consumer with electricity considers the case where the market prices stand exactly like the strike prices during the contract duration. This potential cost is the final cost in the case of a forward contract. Considering the negotiated non-standard RSC, the defined strike prices, the market prices and the traded energy in Month 1, using the compensation scheme presented in Equation 5, the producer has to receive $219.91 \times (-45.32 + 0.5 \times (45.32 - 44.24)) + 0.21 \times (9.92 - 10.34) + \min(0.1 \times (1.52 - 1.54) / 1.52 \times (-45.32 + 0.5 \times (45.32 - 44.24)) + 0.21 \times (9.92 - 10.34), 0.1 \times 45.32) = -9853.78\text{€}$. The consumer has to compute exactly the opposite value and pay to the producer the respectively amount. Comparing with the cost of the forward contract, in this month the consumer saves 112.41€ with the non-standard RSC.

Table 5: Final tariff and compensation from the point of view of the consumer

	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Tariff (€/MWh)	45.32	45.32	45.32	45.32	45.32	45.32
Energy (MWh)	219.91	212.82	219.91	212.82	219.91	212.82
Potential Cost (€)	9966.19	9644.70	9966.19	9644.70	9966.19	9644.70
Elec. Price (€/MWh)	44.24	41.73	42.37	43.89	45.75	47.84
NG Price (€/MWh)	10.34	10.03	11.23	9.49	8.77	8.53
Al. Price (€/kg)	1.54	1.53	1.65	1.55	1.56	1.60
Compensation (€)	-112.41	-383.25	-349.17	-190.50	-31.99	156.44
Final Tariff (€/MWh)	44.81	43.52	43.73	44.42	45.17	46.05
Final Cost (€)	9853.78	9261.45	9617.02	9454.20	9934.20	9801.14

Analyzing table 5 is possible to verify that considering all items' shared risk, and their prices variation in the respective markets, only in Month 6 the producer will not have to compensate the consumer and in the other months is the opposite. So, the consumer has a higher benefit by sharing its risks, paying at the end of the contract a lower amount of money comparing with a tariff without risk-sharing. This happens because only in Month 6 the final tariff is not lower than the electricity strike price (tariff). In Months 5 and 6 the market price of electricity is higher than the tariff. However, in Month 5 the natural gas price is lower than the negotiated strike price, and the aluminum price is higher than the strike price, being the final tariff lower than the electricity price. So, can be concluded that by sharing the risk of the aluminum price (which is always higher than the strike price), the weight of the electricity price reduces in the establishment of the final price. If the consumer has the possibility to trade in spot markets, when comparing the final tariff with the average market price, can be concluded that the consumer only has not benefited from this contract in the last month (Month 6). So, this contract protects the consumer from higher electricity prices, but on the other hand, it loses money when prices fall (if we considered that the consumer can make offers to spot markets). This RSC protects the producer from a fall in the prices and decreases its profit when the prices rise.

Assuming that the tariff is fixed for every type of contract (*i.e.*, keeping

Table 6: The producer's revenue of the different market options in relation to a non-standard RSC.

	Revenue per Month (€)						Revenue k€
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
Non-standard RSC	9853.78	9261.45	9617.02	9454.20	9934.20	9801.14	57.92
DAM	-124.88	-380.55	-299.35	-113.62	126.77	382.20	57.51
Forward	112.41	383.25	349.17	190.50	31.99	-156.44	58.83
DAM+CfD	112.63	383.46	349.39	190.71	32.21	-156.23	58.83
DAM+50% CfD	-6.12	1.45	25.02	38.55	79.49	112.98	58.17

the same tariff) and changing the contract for a standardized one, is going to be performed a comparison of the preliminary economic losses and gains of this contract with the other options: spot markets (DAM), forwards, CfDs and if they (virtually) only share 50% of the electricity price risk (50% CfD). In Table 6 is possible to check the results of this analysis from the point of view of the producer.

Can be verified in Table 6 that the producer has a higher remuneration by signing a fixed tariff, considering a forward agreement, because the prices of electricity are lower than the negotiated strike price, except in Months 5 and 6. Considering that in this study the prices of electricity tend to be lower than the strike price during the next months, CfDs gave a similar result to forwards contracts, but the last has less risk because they have the advantage of hedge against the volatility of spot prices. Considering a mix of spot and financial products, when the prices fall (the case), the producer increases its profit from financial markets (if it sells forwards or CfDs) but decreases it from the spot market (DAM). On the contrary, when the prices rise, it increases its profit from the DAM but decreases it from selling financial products. Furthermore, can be concluded that a mix of trades at spot markets and CfDs is a good option to mitigate risks that producers have in electricity markets. However, while forward agreements increase the risk asymmetry between sellers and buyers of electricity, CfDs balance it, so they can be considered risky from the point of view of consumers. Against this background, the proposed RSC proved to be a better risk hedging option concerning the current market

products.

6. Conclusions

This article has presented several key features of software agents able to negotiate bilateral contracts in energy markets, paying special attention to risk management, notably risk attitude and risk-sharing. In particular, it has described a new type of contract, the Risk-Sharing Contract (RSC), trading strategies and tactics, involving direct modelling of risk attitudes and risk-sharing. RSCs can be used as long-term contracts to hedge against commodity speculation and to support new investments in variable renewable generation. Furthermore, the article has also presented two case studies on bilateral contracting, involving a wind aggregator (seller) and a retailer (buyer) negotiating a yearly contract considering a fixed strike price and quantity, and a producer (seller) and an industrial customer (buyer) negotiating a 24h-rate tariff for the next six months. Both case studies resulted in win-win output for all involved players when negotiating a non-standard RSC concerning other derivative products.

In the first case study, the wind aggregator reduced its profit by 15% concerning the spot market when trading a forward contract with the retailer, which reduced its costs by 3%. If they use a non-standard RSC, the wind aggregator increases its profit by 2% and the retailer reduces its costs by 1% concerning the spot market, obtaining a mutual beneficial agreement. In the second case study, the consumer increased its costs by 2% concerning the spot market when trading both a forward or a contract for differences (CfD) with the producer, which increased its revenues by 2%. If they use a non-standard RSC, the consumer increases its costs by 1% and the producer increases its profit by 1% concerning the spot market. In this case study, the use of the non-standard RSC conducted to a worse agreement to the consumer concerning the spot market. However, it is a better agreement concerning the other derivative products with substantially less risk exposure to the volatility of spot prices.

This new type of contract is a good option to physically trade electricity and can be seen as an alternative to spot and derivatives markets. The RSC proved to hedge against price volatility, and is a good option to market agents whose electricity is essential and has a significant weight in their costs, but is not their main business (for example, customers from the primary sector). For traditional supply-side agents, this type of contract can be used as a form

of risk hedging, but it also decreases their investment return. So, for risk-seeking agents, this type of contract shall be used together with other market options, such as spot markets and CfDs mixes. A long-term non-standard RSC can be used by new investments in variable renewable energy sources, guaranteeing the security that the financial institutions need to finance them without governmental incentives.

The results support the belief that the behaviour of market participants in managing price risk, is as expected, namely the sharing of the potential risks associated with seller and buyer agents. Instead of spot price volatility, risk-sharing shall be directly associated with several other risks, such as commodity price uncertainty, to avoid price risks considering this type of contracts similar to CfDs with physical trade. Also, the shared risk shall be balanced because if an agent supports the majority of the risks with a small shared risk (less than ten percent), the RSC will have similar results to a forward contract. This type of contract can avoid high risks for the parties in the case of sudden rises or falls in commodities prices, decreasing the risk asymmetry of typical contracts. By using this type of contract it is possible to increase the return/risk ratio of the deal, conducting to mutual beneficial agreements. This type of contracts is more beneficial to risk-averse retailers, because it reduces the risk exposure but also the potential profit of market traders. As future work is intended to perform several inter-related experiments to empirically evaluate RSCs, strategies and tactics.

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